

YEAR OF YOUTH AND BUSINESS SUPPORT

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Abstract. The fact that 2024 has been declared the "Year of Youth and Entrepreneurship Support" in Uzbekistan means that we should expect news related to these two areas in the coming months. In recent years, a lot of work has been done to support the personal and professional development of the young generation growing up in our country - these trends will continue.

Key words: public interest, human dignity, professional development, innovative projects, scientific potential, modern economy, educational programs.

"Our main goals are to increase human dignity and worth, to ensure the interests of the population and to build a strong economy"

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his New Year's greetings to the people of Uzbekistan, announced a new year - 2024 as the "Year of supporting youth and business" and thereby wishes to strengthen the role of young people in the socio-economic development of our country and support of entrepreneurship. showed that it exists.

Among these initiatives are the creation of special funds for the financing of innovative projects of young people, the development of entrepreneurship promotion programs and the provision of microcredits.

The importance of young people's active participation in the process of modernization of society through the development of scientific potential and proper education is confirmed in the "Uzbekistan 2030" strategy. Within its framework, it is planned to introduce new educational programs aimed at forming the skills necessary for modern economy and entrepreneurship among young people, and to establish youth small industrial zones that will become a platform for the implementation of entrepreneurial projects. This is not only the development of youth entrepreneurship, but also the creation of new jobs, which means the growth of the country's economy.

An important part of the strategy is to support social and cultural projects aimed at increasing the personal potential of young people. The President emphasizes the need to create conditions for creative and cultural expression of young men and women.

At the same time, supporting young families and solving the problem of divorces is the main focus of the government of Uzbekistan. Counseling programs are offered to strengthen family values. Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his address on the occasion of the New Year holiday, noted that these factors are important in achieving a strong economy and improving the livelihood of the population.

Economic development. It is expected that the economy of Uzbekistan will grow by 5.6-5.8 percent in 2023-2024, and by 6.2-6.4 percent in 2025-2026. This corresponds to the strategic

goal of bringing the GDP per capita to 4 thousand dollars by 2030. It is planned to attract foreign investments to stimulate economic growth and provide necessary capital for business expansion. The President emphasized the importance of developing science, innovation and IT, including the creation of "green" and digital technologies. Creating new jobs and increasing income is a priority.

According to the forecasts of the Asian Development Bank (ADB), the growth of the economy of Uzbekistan in 2024 will be close to 5%. This indicates the stability of industry and agriculture, the flow of investments, which serves to increase the general well-being of the country.

The World Bank predicts that the GDP growth of Uzbekistan will be 5.5-5.8 percent in 2023-2025. These data allow checking the stability of economic development of our republic in the following years.

The foreign economic policy of Uzbekistan is mainly aimed at attracting foreign investments and developing modern technologies. Thus, in the period from 2022 to 2024, it is planned to implement investment projects in Uzbekistan with a total value of about 52.15 billion dollars. In 2024 alone, projects worth 18.2 billion dollars will be implemented (foreign direct investment is 7.73 billion dollars).

It is worth noting that important initiatives have been put forward in the framework of international cooperation in the field of combating corruption in Uzbekistan, the presentation of an international award in this field by the President, the implementation of systematic legal and institutional reforms in this regard, cooperation with the UN, OECD and other prestigious international organizations. The law "On Combating Corruption" was adopted in the republic, an appropriate agency was established, preventive mechanisms aimed at ensuring openness and transparency in the activities of state bodies are being widely implemented.

Declaring 2024 as the "Year of Youth and Entrepreneurship Support" in Uzbekistan is a strategic step aimed at further developing the economy, increasing social stability, and strengthening international relations.

References:

1. https://plovpress.turbopages.org/turbo/plov.press/s/news/lifestyle/god_podderzhki_molodezhi_i_biznesa_v_uzbekistane_cho_to_v_prioritete/
2. https://uza.uz/ru/posts/god-podderzhki-molodezhi-i-biznesa-novaya-glava-v-razviti-uzbekistana_553970
3. <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2024/01/01/year-2024/>
4. Мамуровна, Q. F. (2023). PATRIOTIC EDUCATION OF THE CADETS OF HIGHER MILITARY EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN EXTRA CURRICULUM COURSES. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(5), 254-258.
5. Кадирова Ф.М. (2022). ПОНЯТИЕ ДУХОВНО-ПРАВСТВЕННОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ СУДОВ ВЫСШИХ ВОЕННО-УЧЕБНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЙ И ЕЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ. *Академические исследования в области образования*, 3 (4), 1159-1163. <https://doi.org/10.24412/2181-1385-2022-4-1159-1163>
6. Мамуровна К.Ф. (2022). СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДОЛОГИИ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ КУРСОВ ВЫСШЕГО ВОЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. *Евразийский журнал исследований Atsademis*, 2(2), 160-163.

7. Кадирова Ф.М. (2022). Формы реализации методики воспитания курсантов высших военных учебных заведений на основе духовно-нравственных ценностей. Наука и образование, 3(7), 197-199.
8. Мамуровна К.Ф. (2022). ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ КУРСОВОЙ МЕТОДОЛОГИИ ВОСПИТАНИЯ КУРСАНТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ДУХОВНО-МОРАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ВОЕННЫХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЯХ. НАУЧНЫЙ ОНЛАЙН-ЖУРНАЛ АНАЛИЗ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ, 2(7), 116-118.
9. Мамуровна К.Ф. (2022). Внедрение Методики духовно-нравственного воспитания садов высших военно-учебных заведений в Працице. Журнал педагогических изобретений и практик, 10, 29-31.
10. Мамуровна К.Ф. (2022). Роль и значение командования в воспитании курсантов на основе духовно-нравственных ценностей в высших военно-учебных заведениях. Журнал педагогических изобретений и практик, 10, 32-34.
11. Мамуровна К.Ф. (2022). АНАЛИЗ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УЧЕБНЫХ ПРОГРАММ И МАТЕРИАЛОВ В ВОЕННЫХ ВУЗАХ ВОСПИТАНИЕ КУРСАНТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ДУХОВНО-МОРАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ. Наука и инновации, 1(В4), 71-75.
12. Кадырова Феруза Мамуровна. (2022). СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДОЛОГИИ ДУХОВНО-НРАВСТВЕННОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ КУРСОВ ВОЕННЫХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЙ. ЕВРАЗИЙСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ ATSADEMIS, 2(2), 160-163. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6105905>
13. Кадырова Феруза Мамуровна. (23 апреля 2022 г.). СМИ О СИСТЕМЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. ИННОВАЦИИ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЕ И ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯХ, Канада. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6473815>
14. Qodirova, F. M. (2022). OLIY HARBIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA KURSANTLARNI MA'NAVIY-AXLOQIY QADRIYATLAR ASOSIDA TARBIYALASHDA QO'MONDONLIKNING ROLI. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(6), 213-216.
15. Qodirova, F. (2023). KONSTITUTSIYA-HAYOTIMIZNING, TARAQQIYOTIMIZNING HUQUQIY ASOSI. Бюллетень педагогов нового Узбекистана, 1(12), 21-24.
16. Qodirova, F., & Norboyev, A. (2023). GLOBALLASHUV JARAYONIDA JAMIYATIMIZDA TARBIYA VA MEHNAT TARBIYASINING ANAMIYATI. Бюллетень студентов нового Узбекистана, 1(11), 72-74.

